

**DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADVANCED COMPOSITE
MATERIAL ON VERTICAL STABILIZER
OF F—X AIRCRAFT**

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the main contents of the development of an advanced composite vertical stabilizer for F—X aircraft. Design concept, strength analysis, static and dynamic aeroelastic analysis, fabrication technology, and moulding die, ground and flight test, etc. are described. The paper also recites the design & test data which are useful in practical engineering.

KEYWORDS: Composite; Vertical Stabilizer; Strength Analysis; Stiffness Analysis; Ground Test.

1. **INTRODUCTION**

Chengdu Aircraft Industrial Corporation has been engaged in development of the advanced composite materials since 1980. Up to now, we have successfully fabricated a carbon fiber composite rudder, a vertical stabilizer and a fairing panel for F—X aircraft, which all have been passed the full—scale static test, flight test and certification of China Aerospace Industrial Ministry.

This paper only presents development of a composite vertical stabilizer. The composite vertical stabilizer was designed on the base of the metallic one. The carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin composite was used.

The box of the stabilizer was completely replaced by composite structure, it consists of a composite front spar, a rear spar, ribs and two co—cured skin panels with stringers and reinforced frames of the

access holes, only the main metallic joints and aluminum fairings were retained. The development of the composite vertical stabilizer started in July, 1985, the full-scale static test was passed in Sep., 1989, the flight test had successfully passed through "Large Mach Number" and "Large Slop Turn", etc. totally of 13 flight items in Oct., 1990. The test results validated that the composite vertical stabilizer is equivalent to the metallic one for flight performances. The certification of the Aerospace Industrial Ministry had been passed in Nov., 1990.

In the composite vertical stabilizer, the quantity of the metallic parts being directly replaced by composite was reduced 80%, the quantity of the fasteners was reduced 50%. The weight of the entire stabilizer reduced 20%. Therefore, a good benefit was attained.

This paper presents the structure design of the composite vertical stabilizer, strength and aeroelastic analysis, fabrication technology, ground and flight test.

2. STRUCTURE DESIGN

2.1 Design Criteria Because the composite vertical stabilizer is a direct replacement for the metallic vertical stabilizer, the structure design of the stabilizer must keep its aerodynamic contour, strength, main joints and the paths of the transferring loads, directional stability and controllability, etc., to equal to the metallic vertical stabilizer. Then, the strength and stiffness design of the structure are performed.

2.2 Structure Design Concept In the preliminary design phase, we proposed a lot of structure design concepts. After discussion and selection, we decided to adopt following design concept: the box of the vertical stabilizer was completely replaced by composite structure, it consists of a composite front spar, a rear spar, ribs and two skin panels, stringers and accesses. Only the aluminum front and tip fairing, metallic main spar and side rib, etc. main joints were retained, see Fig. 1.

2.3 Laminate Design According to the requirement of the flight function of the vertical stabilizer, the laminate design of the composite vertical stabilizer employed both "equal stiffness design" and "optimum design with displacement constraints" design methods. Then, the results of the optimum design were used to improve the equal stiffness laminate design of the various composite components, to make them become the best optimum laminate design, possess the best efficiency of the weight

savings. Here, we only show the laminate design of the skin panel, see Fig. 2.

The primary material for the composite vertical stabilizer is carbon fiber/epoxy unidirectional prepreg tape, one ply thickness is 0.125mm.

2.4 Joint Design Front spar, rear spar, ribs, main spar and two skin panels were bonded together with Hi-lock bolts (titanium), HUCK blind bolts and rivets (CRES) and lock bolts (titanium). The spacing between two holes of the fasteners must be $\geq 5.0D$ (D = fastener's diameter) and the edge margin of fastener hole must be $\geq 2.5D$. Co-curing-bonds were used between the skin panels and stringers.

2.5 Design of Environmental Effects and Protection

2.5.1 Lightning Protection The aluminum front and tip fairing, and a metallic tip discharging rod were retained. The conductive straps of the aluminum sheet were grounded to the aluminum parts. They could associate lightning current path.

2.5.2 Galvanic Corrosion Protection In the holes of the fastener, applying adhesive, the fasteners were wet installed; on the interface between carbon laminate and metal, paint or adhesive or glass fabric were used, these measures kept the isolating and sealing interfaces between them, and the galvanic corrosion could be prevented.

2.5.3 Hygrothermal Effect and Damage Protection To account for material strength reduction due to the hygrothermal effect and damage, according to the results of the test, and referring some information, all allowable strength typical properties of the composite material were reduced by a factor of 0.2. That means the design ultimate load was amplified to 125%.

3. STRENGTH ANALYSIS

3.1 Finite Element Stress Analysis The finite element stress analyses of the metallic and composite vertical empennages including a stabilizer and a rudder were performed, using both «Finite Element Analysis Program of metal and composite complex structure METCOMP» compiled by ourselves, and «MSC/NASTRAN Analysis System». The finite element models were both a single empennage and a empennage with a aft fuselage. The single empennage finite element model was shown in Fig. 3. The loading conditions were both "maneuver case" and "gust case".

The Tsai - Wu quadratic failure criteria and the allowable strength

properties to be reduced by a factor of 0.2 as mentioned in 2.5.3 were used to inspect each ply strength of various elements, the minimum safety margin of the First—ply—failure was 0.4. The results showed that the static strength of the composite structure satisfied the design requirement. Comparing the results of these analyses, we found the deformations of the composite vertical empennage were slightly smaller than those of the metal vertical stabilizer. This indicated the stiffness of the composite vertical empennage is better than the metal one.

3.2 Buckling Analysis The quadrilateral plate element of composite skin panels and the shear sheet element of the composite web of the spar and rib were simplified as rectangular elements with four simple supporting sides, the ultimate internal loads were taken from the finite element analysis. Then, the buckling analysis was performed, using «compress and shear buckling analysis program YJCC». The analysis results showed that the initial buckling wouldn't happen until the limit load.

Comparing the buckling analysis results with the test results, we found that both of them were matched well and the test data demonstrated that the skin panel might fail at 133% design ultimate load due to buckling.

3.3 Joint Analysis In the first place, a series of allowable bearing stresses between various fasteners and composite laminates were established by test, using single fastener's specimens. Then, these allowable bearing stresses were used to check the bearing strength of the laminate of the joint location. The conclusion was that the bearing strength of the laminates was enough.

4. STIFFNESS ANALYSIS

Bending and torsional stiffness EI and GJ of both metallic and composite vertical stabilizer were calculated individually by using engineering beam method. Comparison of the results showed that the values of EI and GJ of the composite vertical stabilizer is slightly higher than those of metallic one, that is, the stiffness satisfied the design requirement. Static and dynamic aeroelastic analyses of the metallic and composite vertical empennage (including stabilizer and rudder) were conducted, using «Flutter Analysis Program SUBFLUT» and «Static Aeroelastic Analysis Program SAE1». Analysis results showed that the flutter velocity of the composite vertical empennage was 1.1 times of the flutter velocity of

the metallic one. The minimum static aeroelastic divergent velocity of the composite vertical empennage was 1.5 times of the limit velocity of the aircraft, and the various static derivative efficiencies of the rudder were all in the normal range. These mean that static and dynamic aeroelastic performances of the composite vertical empennage were in accord with design demands.

5. TECHNOLOGY OF FABRICATION AND QUALITY ASSURANCE

Co-curing skin panels reinforced with stringers were manufactured by a mould of the steel thin plate and frame, steel mandrels and rubber soft moulds, see Fig. 4. The advantages of this processing method are as follows: the weight of the mould is lighter, the temperature field of the mould is uniform, the quality of the component could be better. In order to keep the accuracy of the contour of the components and the relative position between skin panel and stringers, layup pre-compaction of the skin panel and stringers was conducted; by pumping vacuum and applying pressure and heat to the layup to remove the excess resin prior to cure. Therefore, during the curing course, the flowability of the resin was reduced, the form of the parts could be maintained, and the slippage of the stringers was more difficult, so that the size accuracy of the component could be guaranteed. Spar and rib channel parts were manufactured by using a metallic male mould and a rubber soft mould, see Fig. 5. The pre-compaction was conducted too. This method is easy to operate and could raise the size accuracy and improve quality of the parts.

The installation of the composite vertical stabilizer was performed on the original jigs used for the metallic one. To assure the quality of the assembly, the controllable feed driller and diamond mechanical tools were used, they had produced excellent holes without the use of a drill backup, the qualified rate of holes achieved 98.8%.

During the entire development, the quality assurance was conducted as required by «HB5342 — 86 COMPOSITE AERONAUTIC TECHNOLOGY QUALITY CONTROL». Various measures were adopted to improve the quality of the product timely. For example, nondestructive inspection was performed, etc.. The success of the full-scale static test and flight test proved that the quality of the product was excellent.

6. TEST

The design development tests of the composite vertical stabilizer, the full—scale static test and flight test were performed as required by 《Military airplane strength and rigidity specification》, the details of the test are as follows.

- 6.1 High Temperature Basic Mechanical Property Tests of Unidirectional Composite The tests demonstrated, at 110°c temperature, the moduli dropped slightly, and the strengthes dropped more than moduli.
- 6.2 Compression and Shear Buckling Test of Skin Panel Reinforced with Stringers The test demonstrated that the buckling strength of the skin panel satisfied the design requirement, their minimum safty margin was 33%.
- 6.3 Joint Tests of Fasteners Allowable bearing stresses between various fasteners and various laminates were obtained, through test by using single hole specimens.
- 6.4 Galvanic Corrosion Test A series galvanic corrosion test of various metal coupling with carbon fiber composite showed that the galvanic corrosion could be prevented by using either isolating or sealing methods.
- 6.5 Hygrothermal Ageing Test Through 240 days hygrothermal ageing test, the strength and stiffness of carbon fiber composite laminates retained about 90%, that indicated CFRP laminate have excellent characteristic to resist ageing erosion.
- 6.6 Dynamic Elastic Moduli Test The test demonstrated that the dynamic moduli of the CFRP laminate is 5~7% more than static moduli, and with frequence increasing, the dynamic moduli increase continually.
- 6.7 Full—scale Static Test The test composite stabilizer with a rudder was installed on the aft fuselage, both maneuver and gust load cases were applied, when the load was applied to 130% of the design ultimate load for maneuver case, the failure of the skin panel compressed occured, the skin panel buckled and the heads of fasteners pulled—thru from the laminates. Buckling failure at this load level was predicted by buckling test. The measure deflection of the composite stabilizer was slightly smaller than that of the metallic stabilizer, that

demonstrated the strength and stiffness of the composite stabilizer were enough.

6.8 Flight Test The flight test of the composite vertical stabilizer was successfully completed on Oct., 1990, through the examination of "Large Mach Number", "Roll", "Aerobatics", "Large-slope-turn", etc. totally 13 items. The results of the flight test indicated that the maneuverability and controllability of the aircraft were good, and the lateral-directional stability was excellent, the magnetic Compass and marker Beacon worked very well, and there wasn't static-interference. Pilot described: the flight performances of the composite vertical stabilizer were equivalent to the metallic vertical stabilizer, and electronic instruments worked well and no static-interference.

7. BENEFIT

7.1 Benefit of Saving Weight The original metallic stabilizer weighs 65.13kg, the composite one weighs 52.29kg, and the ratio of the saving weight is 20%. The weight of the metallic parts being replaced by composite parts is 33.57kg, the weight of the composite parts is 20.73kg, and the ratio of the saving weight is 38.3%. The balance weight on the Aircraft head is correspondently saved by 10.86kg. The total saving weight is 23.7kg. So, the performances of the aircraft have been improved.

7.2 Economic Benefit Because of using co-curing structure, the quantity of parts replaced by composite was reduced 80%, the quantity of fasteners was reduced 50% too. So, the manufacturing equipments and labor of fabrication and assembly must be correspondently reduced. Therefore, when the quantity of the product increase, the manufacturing cost will drop.

8. CONCLUDING REMARKS

From July, 1985 till to Oct., 1990, through 5 years hard work, We had successfully finished all development of an advanced composite vertical stabilizer for F-X aircraft, including flight test and certification of China Aerospace Industrial Ministry. That marks Chengdu Aircraft Industrial Corporation had gotten ability of fabricating independently composite component of the aircraft. The next step, we shall continually produce 3~5 units of the composite vertical stabilizer for future flight

test. At the same time, we shall also perform researches of damage tolerance, fatigue life and repairing technique, and study "aeroelastic tailoring design technique" in depth, and broaden the applying range of the composite on the aircraft continually. Chengdu Aircraft Industrial corporation will be built up a base of application and research of the composite.

you are welcome to visit our corporation and perform technical and academic exchange.

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10. BIOGRAPHY

Shaojian Wang, senior engineer, graduated from Nanjing Aeronautical Institute in 1960. He joined Chengdu Aircraft Industrial Corporation in the same year, where he worked in the Design Department as a stress man and a structure designer.

In 1980, he began to study using the carbon fiber reinforced composite in F—X aircraft, he was responsible for designing a composite rudder, a vertical stabilizer and a fairing panel.

In 1990, the development of the composite rudder, the vertical stabilizer and the fairing panel had been successfully completed, and had been passed the certification of China Aerospace Ministry

Fig. 1 Structure arrangement for F-X composite vertical stabilizer

Fig. 2 Layup of skin panel laminate

Fig. 3 Composite vertical stabilizer with rudder finite element model without aft fuselage.

Fig. 4 Co-curing steel moulding die of skin panel

Fig. 5 Moulding die of rib and spar channel parts

